

Radio Frequency O₂-Plasma Treatment of Carbon Felts: Stoichiometric Insight into O1s and C1s XPS with Correlated Raman and SEM Characterization

For example, consider a C1s spectrum with the following peak contributions:

C=C/C-C: x at. %

C-OH: n_1 at. %

C-O: n_2 at. %

C=O: n_3 at. %

O-C=O: n_4 at. %

The oxygen-bonded carbon contribution can be calculated according to eq. (1) :

$$n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + 2n_4 = N \quad \text{equation (1)}$$

Notably, the carboxyl group (O-C=O) contains two oxygen atoms, thus it contributes to both the O5 peak and to the C=O-related (O1 and O2) peaks.

Normalized group contributions are:

$$\text{C-OH} \quad \mathbf{a_1} \text{at. \%} = \frac{n_1}{N} \times 100 \quad \text{equation (2)}$$

$$\text{C-O} \quad \mathbf{a_2} \text{at. \%} = \frac{n_2}{N} \times 100 \quad \text{equation (3)}$$

$$\text{C=O} \quad \mathbf{a_3} \text{at. \%} = \frac{n_3}{N} \times 100 \quad \text{equation (4)}$$

$$\text{O-C=O} \quad \mathbf{a_4} \text{at. \%} = \frac{n_4}{N} \times 100 \quad \text{equation (5)}$$

$$\text{O-C=O} \quad \mathbf{a_5} \text{at. \%} = \frac{n_4}{N} \times 100 \quad \text{equation (6)}$$

These normalized values from the C1s region should closely correspond to their counterparts in the O1s spectrum:

$$(a_1 + a_2) \text{ in C1s} \approx (O3 + O4) \text{ in O1s} \quad \text{equation (7)}$$

$$(a_3 + a_4) \text{ in C1s} \approx (\text{O1} + \text{O2}) \text{ in O1s} \quad \text{equation (8)}$$

$$(a_5) \text{ in C1s} \approx (\text{O5}) \text{ in O1s} \quad \text{equation (9)}$$

This process is summarized in Table S1.

Table S1. Normalization of the contributions of individual functional groups in the C1s spectrum and their corresponding components in the O1s spectrum

Functional group (C1s)	Contribution (at.%)	Normalization	Corresponding O1s signal
C–OH	n_1	$a_1 = \frac{n_1}{N} \times 100$	O3 + O4
C–O	n_2	$a_2 = \frac{n_2}{N} \times 100$	O3 + O4
C=O	n_3	$a_3 = \frac{n_3}{N} \times 100$	O1 + O2
O–C=O (carbonyl O)	n_4	$a_4 = \frac{n_4}{N} \times 100$	O1 + O2
O–C=O (carboxyl O)	n_4	$a_5 = \frac{n_2}{N} \times 100$	O5

Example for calculation of peak-fitting validation procedure (sample treated at 50 W for 2.5 min).

Derived from C1s:

C=C/C–C: 60.3 at.%

C–OH: 6.4 at.% = n_1

C–O: 22.6 at.% = n_2

C=O: 6.6 at.% = n_3

O–C=O: 4.2 at.% = n_4

The oxygen-bonded carbon contribution is:

$$N = n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + 2n_4 = 6.4 + 22.6 + 6.6 + 2(4.2) = 44.0 \text{ at.}\%$$

Normalized group contributions:

$$a_1 (\text{C-OH}): (6.4 / 44.0) \times 100 = 15.5 \text{ at.}\%$$

$$a_2 (\text{C-O}): (22.6 / 44.0) \times 100 = 51.4 \text{ at.}\%$$

$$a_3 (\text{C=O}): (6.6 / 44.0) \times 100 = 15.0 \text{ at.}\%$$

$$a_4 (\text{O-C=O}): (4.2 / 44.0) \times 100 = 9.5 \text{ at.}\%$$

$$a_5 (\text{O-C=O}): 9.5 \text{ at.}\%$$

These normalized values from the C1s region should closely correspond to their counterparts in the O1s spectrum:

$$(a_1 + a_2) \text{ in C1s} \approx (\text{O3} + \text{O4}) \text{ in O1s} : 66.9 \approx 63.3$$

$$(a_3 + a_4) \text{ in C1s} \approx (\text{O1} + \text{O2}) \text{ in O1s} : 24.5 \approx 23.5$$

$$(a_5) \text{ in C1s} \approx (\text{O5}) \text{ in O1s} : 9.5 \approx 9.4$$

Table S2. lists the normalization process for quantifying the contributions of different oxygen-bonded carbon groups in the C1s spectra of pristine and O₂ plasma-treated carbon felts. The table reports the atomic percentages of each functional group, including C-OH (n₁), C-O (n₂), C=O (n₃), and O-C=O (n₄, n₅), along with the total oxygen-bonded carbon fraction (N = Σn_i). To enable comparison across samples, the contributions of each group are then normalized to N, yielding the relative values a₁-a₅. These normalized fractions represent the proportional share of each functionality within the total oxygen-bonded carbon signal in the C1s region.

The stoichiometric validation in Table S3. demonstrates excellent agreement between the correlated C1s and O1s components. Across all treatment conditions, the ratios (a₁ + a₂)/(O3 + O4), (a₃ + a₄)/(O1 + O2), and a₅/O5 remain close to unity (≈ 0.9-1.1). This confirms that the peak-fitting approach is reasonable and consistent. The small deviations observed (≤ 10 %) can be ascribed to peak overlap in the O1s region, and minor contributions from physisorbed oxygen. Notably, the stability of these ratios across plasma powers and treatment times indicates that even as the total oxygen content varies, the relative assignment of oxygen species in C1s and O1s remains reliable.

Table S2. Normalization of the contributions of individual functional groups in the C1s spectrum of pristine and O₂-plasma treated carbon felts and their corresponding components in the O1s spectrum.

Power (W)	Duration (min)	n ₁ : C-OH	n ₂ : C-O	n ₃ : C=O	n ₄ : O-C=O	n ₅ : O-C=O	N : $\sum_1^5 n$	a ₁ : n ₁ /N	a ₂ : n ₂ /N	a ₃ : n ₃ /N	a ₄ : n ₄ /N	a ₅ : n ₄ /N
Pristine	0	6.4	5.1	2.4	1.6	1.6	17.2	37.1	29.9	14.1	9.4	9.4
50	2.5	6.4	22.6	6.6	4.2	4.2	43.8	14.5	51.5	15.0	9.5	9.5
75		10.7	23.7	5.8	6.1	6.1	52.4	20.4	45.1	11.1	11.7	11.7
100		10.9	23.6	5.5	6.2	6.2	52.5	20.7	45.0	10.5	11.9	11.9
150		16.7	5.4	5.2	4.0	4.0	35.3	47.3	15.3	14.7	11.4	11.4
200		16.7	6.3	5.0	5.8	5.8	39.7	42.2	16.0	12.7	14.6	14.6
50	5	9.4	28.7	5.6	7.3	7.3	58.5	16.1	49.1	9.6	12.6	12.6
75		11.8	28.9	5.9	12.2	12.2	70.9	16.6	40.7	8.4	17.2	17.2
100		12.2	28.0	5.4	11.8	11.8	69.2	17.6	40.5	7.8	17.1	17.1
150		13.2	5.0	5.3	5.3	5.3	34.2	38.7	14.6	15.5	15.6	15.6
200		11.6	5.2	3.1	5.5	5.5	30.8	37.6	16.8	10.1	17.7	17.7

Table S3. Validation of C1s and O1s peak assignments through stoichiometric correlation

Power (W)	Duration	a ₁ +a ₂	a ₃ +a ₄	a ₅	O ₃ +O ₄	O ₁ +O ₂	O ₅	(a ₁ +a ₂)/(O ₃ +O ₄)	(a ₃ +a ₄)/(O ₁ +O ₂)	a ₅ /O ₅
Pristine	0	67.0	23.6	9.4	62.5	21.5	8.3	1.1	1.1	1.1
50	2.5	66.1	24.5	9.5	64.35	23.5	9.42	1.0	1.0	1.0
75		65.5	22.8	11.7	65.3	21.04	11.25	1.0	1.1	1.0
100		65.7	22.4	11.9	64.24	20.68	12.66	1.0	1.1	0.9
150		62.6	26.0	11.4	57.93	24.12	10.72	1.1	1.1	1.1
200		58.2	27.3	14.6	53.33	25.45	13.99	1.1	1.1	1.0
50	5	65.3	22.2	12.6	62.59	21.61	12.56	1.0	1.0	1.0
75		57.3	25.5	17.2	57.37	24.57	15.92	1.0	1.0	1.1
100		58.1	24.8	17.1	55.48	23.91	15.85	1.0	1.0	1.1
150		53.3	31.1	15.6	48.55	29.29	15.21	1.1	1.1	1.0
200		54.4	27.9	17.7	48.92	27.96	16.07	1.1	1.0	1.1

Additional SEM micrographs of the O₂ plasma-treated carbon felts are shown here at lower magnification. The images were taken from the same spots as in the main manuscript, but with a wider field of view. They provide an overview of the larger surface structure and confirm that the changes seen at higher magnification are representative of the overall morphology.

Figure. S1. SEM micrographs of (a) pristine and (b–k) O₂ plasma-treated carbon felts subjected to plasma powers of 50–200 W for treatment durations of (b–f) 2.5 min and (g–k) 5 min.